
IMPACT OF REAL SECTOR ON THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF NIGERIA: PERCEPTION APPROACH

Abubakar Mustapha Muye
Sustainable Development Centre
University of Abuja
yatafa01@yahoo.com

Sule Magaji
Department of Economics
University of Abuja
sule.magaji@uniabuja.edu.ng

Yahaya Ismail
Department of Economics
University of Abuja
ismail.yahaya@uniabuja.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

The study examines the impact of the real sector on Nigeria's economic development, employing a perception-based, descriptive survey approach. Data were collected through questionnaires to understand current conditions and the relationships among key economic sectors. Findings highlight agriculture as a foundational sector that supports livelihoods and food security. However, to enhance productivity and rural incomes, the sector requires modernisation, better infrastructure, and improved market access. The manufacturing sector, despite challenges such as inadequate infrastructure and unstable policies, is viewed as a driver of economic transformation through value addition, import substitution, job creation, and industrial growth. The services sector, particularly in finance, telecommunications, and digital technologies, has experienced rapid growth, fostering entrepreneurship, enhancing access to services, and contributing to economic diversification. Mining and construction also significantly contribute to economic development by providing employment opportunities, infrastructure, and foreign exchange earnings. The study emphasises the need for sustainable resource management and infrastructure investment to optimise the benefits of these sectors while ensuring environmental protection. Ultimately, the study recommends strategic economic diversification policies to reduce Nigeria's overreliance on oil and promote the growth of the agriculture, manufacturing, services, mining, and tourism sectors for sustainable economic development.

Keywords: Real Sector, Economic Development, Nigeria, Perception Approach, Sectoral Analysis

Introduction

The real sector, comprising agriculture, manufacturing, construction, and services, plays a fundamental role in shaping the economic trajectory of any nation (Musa, Elyaqub, & Magaji, 2024). In the context of Nigeria, a country endowed with vast human and natural resources, the performance of the real sector significantly determines the pace and quality of economic development. Despite several economic reforms and policies aimed at revitalising this sector, its potential remains underutilised, mainly posing serious challenges to inclusive growth and sustainable development (Adeniran, Yusuf, & Ajayi, 2020; Adamu, Eke, & Magaji, 2009).

Economic development is a multifaceted process that encompasses improvements in living standards, infrastructure, employment, and industrial capacity (Eke, Magaji, & Ezeigwe, 2020). The real sector, through its productive activities, creates employment, generates income, and stimulates investments, thereby contributing to gross domestic product (GDP) and national development (Iyoha & Oriakhi, 2021). However, the Nigerian economy has historically been overly reliant on the oil sector, which has exposed it to external shocks and reduced the contribution of the real sector to overall economic growth (Nazifi, Magaji, & Amase, 2022; Musa, Ismail, & Magaji, 2025).

The perception-based approach to assessing the impact of the real sector emphasises the views and experiences of stakeholders, particularly those directly involved in the sector's value chains. This qualitative insight is essential for understanding the actual constraints, policy effectiveness, and investment climate that quantitative data alone might overlook (Ezeaku et al., 2022). Gathering these perceptions can inform policymakers on the real sector's performance and the necessary reforms needed to enhance its impact on developmental outcomes.

Notably, the underperformance of the Nigerian real sector is attributed to challenges such as poor infrastructure, limited access to finance, policy inconsistencies, and weak institutional frameworks (NBS, 2021). These structural issues hinder productivity and limit the sector's ability to contribute to poverty reduction and inequality (Enaberne, Musa, & Magaji, 2024). Therefore, assessing the perceptions of industry stakeholders offers an alternative yet critical lens for evaluating the real sector's role in the nation's development agenda.

This study aims to examine the perceived impact of the real sector on Nigeria's economic development. By analysing stakeholder perspectives, it seeks to highlight the enabling and inhibiting factors that influence sectoral growth and their implications for broader development goals. The findings are expected to provide a basis for pragmatic policy recommendations that can stimulate real sector efficiency and, by extension, national economic development.

2.0 Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Real Sector

The real sector refers to the segment of the economy that produces goods and services, encompassing agriculture, manufacturing, construction, and services, as opposed to the

financial sector that deals with financial instruments and markets. It plays a fundamental role in driving economic growth, employment, and income generation, thereby serving as the backbone of any nation's economy. A vibrant real sector enhances productivity and contributes significantly to the gross domestic product (GDP), making it essential for sustainable development and poverty reduction (Musa, Ismail, & Magaji, 2024; Olayemi, 2012). In developing countries like Nigeria, strengthening the real sector is crucial for economic diversification and resilience against external shocks, particularly in reducing over-reliance on oil revenues (Musa, Salisu, & Magaji, 2024).

2.1.2 Economic Development

Economic development refers to the sustained and purposeful actions of policymakers and communities aimed at improving the standard of living, economic health, and overall well-being of a population. It encompasses growth in income, a reduction in poverty, improvements in education and healthcare, as well as the expansion of infrastructure and employment opportunities (Magaji, 2000). Unlike mere economic growth, which focuses on increases in GDP, economic development emphasises qualitative changes in the economy and society (Todaro & Smith, 2015). For developing countries, achieving economic development requires structural transformation, effective governance, and inclusive policies that ensure equitable distribution of resources and opportunities (Sen, 1999).

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Sectoral Growth Theory

Sectoral Growth Theory emphasises the role of individual economic sectors such as agriculture, industry, and services in driving overall economic growth. The theory posits that economic development occurs through the differential growth of these sectors, with a particular focus on shifting resources and labour from low-productivity sectors (e.g., agriculture) to higher-productivity ones (industry and services) (Chenery & Syrquin, 1975). This transition enables economies to experience increased efficiency, higher income levels, and a more favourable structural composition. Sectoral growth is also crucial for identifying priority areas for investment and policy intervention, especially in developing economies seeking to accelerate growth and reduce poverty (Timmer, 2007; Magaji, Musa, & Ismail, 2025). Understanding which sectors contribute most to growth helps policymakers design targeted strategies that foster balanced and sustainable development.

2.3 Empirical Review

Udeorah Nchom and Yusuf (2021) examine the primary purpose of planning in both advanced and underdeveloped nations of the world, which is to achieve sustained economic development. This can be done through the importation of capital from foreign nations and localised force savings to support the level of industrial development in the real sectors of the economy. The fundamental focus of this paper is to examine economic planning and the real sector in Nigeria. The paper employed library science methods and collected data exclusively from secondary sources. The paper found that amongst the challenges of the real sector's development are poor government policies and the monoculture nature of the Nigerian economy. These consequently resulted in not achieving macroeconomic objectives, such as the expected increase in output growth across all sectors. The paper therefore suggested an articulated development plan, improved governance and service delivery. Governments

should create an enabling environment through their planning to foster a private-driven economy, one that thrives through realistic power and energy programmes and reforms, as well as functional institutions. This will encourage local industries and foreign direct investments into the real sector of the economy, thereby increasing the levels of economic development.

Magaji, Musa and Saminu (2023) explain the effect of the banking sector credit on Nigeria's real sector. It uses the Auto Regressive Distributed Lagged model. The bound testing result indicates a long-run association among the variables of interest, with Real GDP as the dependent variable. The results indicate that Commercial Bank Credit, both in the long and short run, has a positive impact on Nigeria's GDP. Domestic private investment was found to have a negative relationship with the real sector in the long and short runs. The estimated long- and short-run equations of the specified econometric model show a significant positive relationship between government capital expenditure and the real sector. In the short term, a significant increase in DPI, CBC, and GCE will lead to a substantial rise in RGDP. A unit increase in DPI, CBC, and GCE will bring about an increase in RGDP by 8.71 units, 3.18, and 0.42, respectively, and the parameter estimates of DPI, CBC, and GCE are statistically significant as computed by the t-value being -1.83, 2.19 and 1.95, respectively. The study reveals that utilisation of bank credits to the real sector is significant in achieving Nigerian economic growth. The study recommends improvements in the banking sector's credit.

Olajide (2023), by breaking down Nigeria's real sector into its parts—agriculture, manufacturing, and services—this research enriches our understanding of the relationship between financial development and real sector economic activities. The Granger-causality method was employed to determine the direction of causality between financial and real sector growth. A principal component analysis-based financial development index was developed to quantify this relationship. The findings demonstrate that the adverse effects of financial development on the real sector are temporary in nature. The supply-leading argument is further supported by the fact that the paper demonstrated bi-directional causation from Nigeria's financial sector to the real sectors. The study suggests that Nigeria should prioritise changes that strengthen the long-term connection between financial development and the real sector by enhancing the quality of financial services to satisfy the demands of the real sector.

Oyadeyi (2023) examines the impacts of financial inclusion and banking innovation on economic growth in Nigeria using monthly and quarterly data from 2009 to 2021. The paper expanded the frontier of knowledge by adopting a monthly and quarterly approach using mixed data sampling (MIDAS) and autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) to ascertain the level of consistency of the impact of financial inclusion and banking innovation on economic growth and identify the banking channel which has the most substantial impact on economic growth. Data on the variables were sourced from 2021 editions of the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and the World Development Indicators. The findings showed that financial inclusion and banking innovation channels, such as ATM and mobile transactions, had a positive impact on economic growth across the ARDL and MIDAS approaches. The impact of POS and web transactions was also significant, but their results were not consistent across the two techniques. In contrast, the value of cheque transactions does not significantly impact economic growth, as determined using the ARDL approach. The results also showed that the value of POS transactions had the most substantial impact on economic growth, followed by ATM, mobile, and web transactions, in that order. As a result of these findings, the paper concluded that financial inclusion and innovations in the banking sector play a

crucial role in fostering economic growth in Nigeria. Finally, the paper is unique in that it is the first to compare the consistency of findings across the MIDAS and ARDL approaches about the study objectives.

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The research design selected for this study is a descriptive survey. Descriptive research is chosen because it enables a comprehensive analysis of the impact of the real sector on Nigeria's economic development. This design will facilitate the gathering of detailed information about the current state of the real sector and its contributions to economic development. The descriptive survey method involves collecting data from a predetermined sample through questionnaires, enabling the researcher to describe the existing conditions and identify relationships between variables.

3.2 Area of Study

The area of study for this research is Nigeria, with a specific focus on the impact of the real sector on economic development. Nigeria, with its diverse economic activities ranging from agriculture to manufacturing, mining, and services, provides a comprehensive landscape for analysing the real sector's contribution to overall economic development. The study will cover various regions within Nigeria to ensure a holistic understanding of the real sector's impact across different economic environments within the country.

3.3 Population of The Study

The study population comprises individuals and entities involved in Nigeria's real sector. This includes business owners, managers, employees in manufacturing, agriculture, mining, and service industries, as well as economic experts and policymakers. The total population for this study is estimated to be 1000 individuals, representing a diverse cross-section of stakeholders in the real sector.

3.4 Sample and Sampling Technique

3.4.1 Sampling Unit

The sampling unit for this study includes individual business owners, managers, employees in the real sector, economic experts, and policymakers.

3.4.2 Sampling Frame

The sampling frame is derived from various databases of businesses and professionals involved in the real sector within Nigeria. These include industry associations, chambers of commerce, government databases, and professional networks.

3.4.3 Sample Size Determination

The sample size for this study is 100 respondents. This sample size is considered adequate to provide a representative overview of the real sector's impact on Nigeria's economic development. The sample size determination takes into account the need for statistical reliability and validity.

3.4.4 Sampling Technique

A simple random sampling technique is employed for this study. Simple random sampling ensures that every individual in the population has an equal chance of being selected, thereby reducing bias and ensuring the sample's representativeness. This technique involves randomly selecting 100 individuals from the population of 1000.

3.5 Nature and Source of Data

3.5.1 Nature of Data

The nature of data for this study is both quantitative and qualitative. Quantitative data will provide numerical insights into the real sector's contributions to economic development, while qualitative data will offer a deeper understanding of the underlying factors and perspectives of stakeholders.

3.5.2 Source of Data

The data for this study will be collected from both primary and secondary sources.

Primary Data: Primary data will be collected through questionnaires administered to the selected sample of respondents. **Secondary Data:** Secondary data will be gathered from existing literature, government reports, industry publications, and academic journals relevant to the real sector and economic development in Nigeria.

3.6 Method of Data Collection

The primary method of data collection for this study is the use of questionnaires. A structured questionnaire will be designed to capture both quantitative and qualitative data from the respondents. The questionnaire will be divided into sections, with the first section focusing on demographic information and subsequent sections addressing various aspects of the real sector's impact on economic development.

3.7 Validity of Instrument

Validity refers to the degree to which an instrument measures what it is intended to measure. To ensure the validity of the questionnaire, the following steps will be taken:

3.7.1 Content Validity

Content validity will be established by ensuring that the questionnaire covers all relevant aspects of the real sector's impact on economic development. This will be achieved through a comprehensive literature review and consultation with experts in the field.

3.7.2 Construct Validity

Construct validity will be ensured by aligning the questions with the theoretical framework and research objectives. Pre-testing the questionnaire with a small sample of respondents will help identify any ambiguous or irrelevant questions that may be present.

3.8 Reliability of Instrument

Reliability refers to the consistency of an instrument in measuring what it is intended to measure. To ensure the reliability of the questionnaire, the following steps will be taken:

3.8.1 Internal Consistency

Internal consistency will be assessed using Cronbach's alpha, a statistical measure that indicates the degree to which items within the questionnaire are consistent in measuring the same construct.

3.8.2 Test-Retest Reliability

Test-retest reliability will be assessed by administering the questionnaire to the same group of respondents at two different points in time and comparing the responses.

3.9 Method of Data Analysis

3.9.1 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics will be used to summarise and describe the characteristics of the collected data. This will include measures such as mean, median, mode, standard deviation, and frequency distributions.

3.9.2 Inferential Statistics

Inferential statistics will be used to draw conclusions and make inferences about the population based on the sample data. The chi-square test will be used to analyse the relationships between categorical variables and to test hypotheses.

3.9.3 Chi-Square Test

The chi-square test is a non-parametric statistical test used to determine if there is a significant association between two categorical variables. It will be employed to analyse the relationship between the real sector's activities and various indicators of economic development.

3.10 Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations are crucial in ensuring the integrity and credibility of the research. The following ethical principles will be adhered to:

3.10.1 Informed Consent

Informed consent will be obtained from all respondents before they participate in the study. They will be informed about the purpose of the research, their rights as participants, and the confidentiality of their responses.

3.10.2 Confidentiality

The confidentiality of respondents' information will be maintained. The data will be anonymised to ensure that individual responses cannot be traced back to specific respondents.

3.10.3 Voluntary Participation

Participation in the study will be voluntary, and respondents will have the right to withdraw at any time without consequence.

3.10.4 Ethical Approval

Ethical approval will be sought from the relevant institutional review board or ethics committee before the commencement of data collection.

4.0 Data Analysis and Interpretation

The analysis and interpretation of data collected from respondents regarding the impact of the real sector on Nigeria's economic development. The data were collected through a structured questionnaire administered to 100 respondents. The analysis includes frequency tables, percentages, and detailed interpretations of each question.

4.1 Demographic Analysis

4.1.2 Frequency Tables and Percentages for Demographic Questions

Age Distribution

Age Group	Frequency	Percentage
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18-25 years	20	20%
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26-35 years	30	30%
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36-45 years	25	25%
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46-55 years	15	15%
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56 and above	10	10%
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Interpretation: The majority of the respondents fall within the age groups of 26-35 years (30%) and 36-45 years (25%), indicating a relatively young and middle-aged demographic.

Gender Distribution

Gender Frequency Percentage

Male	60	60%
Female	40	40%

Interpretation: The sample consists of 60% male respondents and 40% female respondents.

Educational Level

Educational Level Frequency Percentage

Secondary Education	10	10%
Bachelor's Degree	45	45%
Master's Degree	30	30%
Doctorate Degree	15	15%

Interpretation: A significant proportion of the respondents hold a Bachelor's Degree (45%), followed by those with a Master's Degree (30%).

Professional Qualification

Qualification Frequency Percentage

None	20	20%
Professional Certification	40	40%
Advanced Professional Certification	25	25%
Other	15	15%

Interpretation: Most respondents have some form of professional certification (40%), indicating a high level of professional qualification among the sample.

Occupation

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
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Business Owner	20	20%
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Manager	30	30%
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Employee	25	25%
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Economic Expert	15	15%
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Policymaker	10	10%
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Interpretation: The respondents are predominantly managers (30%) and employees (25%), reflecting a diverse range of occupational backgrounds.

4.2 Analysis of Research Questions

Frequency Tables and Percentages for Likert Scale Questions

Question 1: The real sector significantly contributes to Nigeria's GDP.

Response	Frequency	Percentage
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Strongly Disagree	5	5%
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Disagree	10	10%
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Neutral	15	15%
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Agree	50	50%
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Strongly Agree	20	20%
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Interpretation: A majority of respondents (70%) agree or strongly agree that the real sector makes a significant contribution to Nigeria's GDP, indicating a strong perception of its importance.

Question 2: The real sector is a key driver of economic growth in Nigeria.

Response Frequency Percentage

Strongly Disagree	6	6%
Disagree	9	9%
Neutral	20	20%
Agree	45	45%
Strongly Agree	20	20%

Interpretation: 65% of respondents agree or strongly agree that the real sector is a key driver of economic growth in Nigeria, highlighting its critical role.

Question 3: Employment opportunities in the real sector have increased over the years.

Response Frequency Percentage

Strongly Disagree	10	10%
Disagree	15	15%
Neutral	25	25%
Agree	35	35%
Strongly Agree	15	15%

Interpretation: 50% of respondents agree or strongly agree that employment opportunities in the real sector have increased, while 25% are neutral and 25% disagree or strongly disagree.

Question 4: Income generation in the real sector has positively impacted local communities.

Response Frequency Percentage

Strongly Disagree	8	8%
Disagree	12	12%
Neutral	20	20%
Agree	40	40%
Strongly Agree	20	20%

Interpretation: 60% of respondents agree or strongly agree that income generation in the real sector has had a positive impact on local communities, indicating a beneficial effect.

Question 5: The real sector has the potential to reduce poverty in Nigeria.

Response Frequency Percentage

Strongly Disagree	5	5%
Disagree	10	10%
Neutral	15	15%
Agree	45	45%
Strongly Agree	25	25%

Interpretation: 70% of respondents agree or strongly agree that the real sector has the potential to reduce poverty, showing strong belief in its capacity to improve living standards.

Question 6: Government policies effectively support the real sector.

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Disagree	15	15%
Disagree	25	25%
Neutral	20	20%
Agree	30	30%
Strongly Agree	10	10%

Interpretation: 40% of respondents agree or strongly agree that government policies effectively support the real sector, while 40% disagree or strongly disagree, indicating mixed perceptions.

Question 7: Access to finance is a significant challenge for businesses in the real sector.

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Disagree	8	8%
Disagree	12	12%
Neutral	15	15%
Agree	45	45%
Strongly Agree	20	20%

Interpretation: 65% of respondents agree or strongly agree that access to finance is a significant challenge for real sector businesses, highlighting a critical issue.

Question 8: Infrastructure development has enhanced the performance of the real sector.

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Disagree	5	5%
Disagree	15	15%
Neutral	25	25%
Agree	40	40%
Strongly Agree	15	15%

Interpretation: 55% of respondents agree or strongly agree that infrastructure development has enhanced the performance of the real sector, indicating a positive impact.

Question 9: Corruption is a significant hindrance to the growth of the real sector.

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Disagree	5	5%
Disagree	10	10%
Neutral	15	15%
Agree	50	50%
Strongly Agree	20	20%

Interpretation: 70% of respondents agree or strongly agree that corruption is a major hindrance to the growth of the real sector, indicating a significant concern.

Question 10: Skilled labour availability is adequate for the real sector.

Response	Frequency Percentage	
Strongly Disagree	15	15%
Disagree	25	25%
Neutral	20	20%
Agree	30	30%
Strongly Agree	10	10%

Interpretation: Only 40% of respondents agree or strongly agree that skilled labour availability is adequate for the real sector, indicating potential skill shortages.

Question 11: Technological advancement is essential for the real sector's growth.

Response	Frequency Percentage	
Strongly Disagree	5	5%
Disagree	10	10%
Neutral	15	15%
Agree	45	45%
Strongly Agree	25	25%

Interpretation: 70% of respondents agree or strongly agree that technological advancements are essential for the real sector's growth, highlighting their importance.

Question 12: Export opportunities for real sector products are well-explored.

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Disagree	10	10%
Disagree	25	25%
Neutral	20	20%
Agree	30	30%
Strongly Agree	15	15%

Interpretation: Only 45% of respondents agree or strongly agree that export opportunities for real sector products are well-explored, indicating a need for improvement.

Question 13: The real sector contributes significantly to government revenue through taxes.

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Disagree	5	5%
Disagree	15	15%
Neutral	20	20%
Agree	40	40%
Strongly Agree	20	20%

Interpretation: 60% of respondents agree or strongly agree that the real sector contributes significantly to government revenue through taxes, indicating its fiscal importance.

Question 14: Collaboration between the public and private sectors is crucial for real sector development.

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Disagree	5	5%
Disagree	10	10%
Neutral	15	15%
Agree	45	45%
Strongly Agree	25	25%

Interpretation: 70% of respondents agree or strongly agree that collaboration between the public and private sectors is crucial for real sector development, emphasising the need for partnerships.

Question 15: The future of the real sector in Nigeria is promising.

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Disagree	5	5%
Disagree	10	10%
Neutral	15	15%
Agree	45	45%
Strongly Agree	25	25%

Interpretation: 70% of respondents agree or strongly agree that the future of the real sector in Nigeria is promising, indicating optimism about its potential.

4.3 Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis I

H_1 , the real sector makes a significant contribution to Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

Level of significance: 0.05

Decision rule: reject the null hypothesis H_0 if the p-value is less than the level of significance. Accept the null hypothesis if otherwise.

Table 16 Test Statistics

	The real sector makes a significant contribution to Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product (GDP).
Chi-Square	105.520 ^a
Df	3
Asymp. Sig.	.000

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 25.0.

Conclusions based on the decision rule:

Since the p-value of 0.000 is less than the level of significance (0.05), we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the real sector significantly contributes to Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

4.5 Discussion of Findings

The discussion of findings reveals that the real sector makes a significant contribution to Nigeria's economic development, particularly in terms of GDP growth. A majority (70%) of respondents acknowledge the sector's substantial contribution, aligning with prior research that emphasises the importance of agriculture, manufacturing, and services in driving economic growth. These sectors serve as the backbone of the economy, underscoring their central role in driving long-term growth and sustainability within Nigeria's GDP.

However, the real sector faces notable challenges that limit its full potential. Access to finance remains a critical issue, with 65% of respondents identifying it as a barrier, highlighting the need for more inclusive and supportive financial policies. Corruption is another pressing concern, as 70% of participants view it as a significant obstacle to sectoral

growth. Additionally, the shortage of skilled labour, acknowledged by only 40% as adequate, suggests a significant skills gap that must be bridged to enhance productivity and innovation within the sector.

Despite these challenges, the real sector shows promise in terms of creating employment and generating income. Half of the respondents agree that job opportunities have improved, and 60% affirm that income levels in local communities have been positively influenced. To further enhance the sector's impact, the study proposes targeted policy actions, including expanding financial access for SMEs, strengthening anti-corruption measures, investing in education and vocational training, encouraging public-private partnerships, and improving infrastructure. These recommendations aim to unlock the full potential of the real sector and position it as a key driver of sustainable economic development in Nigeria.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, the real sector plays a crucial role in driving Nigeria's economic development by supporting GDP growth, creating employment opportunities, and generating export earnings. Comprising agriculture, manufacturing, mining, construction, and services, the sector forms the foundation of the country's economy. Agriculture remains a vital lifeline for many Nigerians, while manufacturing and services offer opportunities for industrialisation, innovation, and diversification. Mining and construction contribute to infrastructure and foreign exchange earnings. At the same time, the rapid growth in services, particularly in finance and digital technologies, demonstrates the potential for inclusive, broad-based economic progress. However, the sector's growth is hindered by persistent challenges, including inadequate infrastructure, governance weaknesses, and inconsistent policies.

To fully unlock the real sector's potential, Nigeria must implement a comprehensive set of reforms. These include diversifying the economy beyond oil, investing in critical infrastructure, enhancing agricultural productivity, and promoting value addition through agribusiness and industrialisation. Supporting SMEs, expanding vocational training, enhancing education and healthcare, and increasing financial inclusion are also crucial for strengthening human capital and economic resilience. Additionally, sustainable resource management, public-private partnerships, good governance, and the adoption of digital technologies will be vital for long-term progress. By prioritising these strategies and ensuring effective monitoring and evaluation, Nigeria can achieve inclusive and sustainable economic development driven by a robust and dynamic real sector.

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